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Editorial

FEMINIST THEOLOGIES **Altering the Theological Landscape**

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“There is no longer Jew or Greek, there is no longer slave and free, there is no longer male and female; for all of you are one in Christ Jesus” (Gal 3:28; LG 32) is one of the core dictums of Christianity on human dignity and equality. It has not been an easy path for Christianity to actualize the radical equality preached in the early centuries. Feminist theology endeavours to play a part in the midwifery of a theology that promotes gender justice, equality, and liberation on behalf of the Church, even if it must critically evaluate the Church itself. “Women’s experiences” is the starting point of feminist theological inquiries. Women’s perspectives become key to critically examining traditions, scriptures, and religious and social practices. Feminist theology is suspicious of any theology, which claims to be universal and timeless because it recognizes the role of history and patriarchal social structures in shaping theological thoughts. It is founded on the Church’s understanding that discrimination based on sex is contrary to God’s design (GS 29) and, more so, that all human persons are being created equal in God’s image (Gen 1:27).

Feminist consciousness is not limited to Christianity but found in men and women across religious traditions and civil sectors. Feminist theology developed significantly in the Christian context, most probably as a response to the overwhelmingly male dominated long established theological, canonical, and rigid clerical hierarchy. It arose not only as an academic discipline but also as a challenge to: who owns and holds the right to speak about God, morality, and human dignity. It is more accurate to use 'feminist theologies' rather than 'feminist theology' because there is a wide spectrum of feminist thoughts as well as varied contexts. If one end of the spectrum aligns with Christ's values, then the other end may potentially do the opposite. Even within India, women do not share a homogeneous context; therefore, it is nearly impossible to formulate a single, homogeneous feminist theology.

1. HISTORICAL GLIMPSES OF FEMINIST THEOLOGIES

Feminist theologies are relatively young as a theological discipline, tracing its roots back to the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. However, glimpses of feminist thoughts are visible from the early centuries. Christianity has witnessed a *diakonos*, Phoebe (Rom 16:1-2); house-Church leaders and preachers, Aquila and Prisca (1 Cor 16:19; Acts 18:24-26); a fourth-century philosopher and theologian, Macrina the Younger; a twelfth-century preacher and theologian, Hildegard of Bingen; fifteenth and sixteenth centuries religious women like Angela Merici and Mary Ward who initiated new ways of religious life for women. The women mentioned and many more have expressed feminist ideas across centuries.

Initially organized women's movements began questioning women's exclusion from religious leadership and theological education. The women activists and scholars confronted the justification of female subordination, be

it in Scripture, marriage, Church leadership or public life. One of the fitting examples of that period is Elizabeth Cady Stanton. The main objective of her work, *The Women's Bible* (1895–1898), was to interpret or reinterpret “texts and chapters that directly refer to women, as well as those in which women are made prominent by exclusion.” She had no formal theological training; however, her work represents an important proto-feminist theological critique. At the same time, Anna Julia Cooper, an American black woman, linked Christian thoughts with concerns about race and gender in her celebrated work, *A Voice from the South* (1892). Her work anticipated later development in womanist theology for the black context. Such endeavours laid the foundation for feminist theologies, even though they had not yet emerged as a distinct academic discipline.

It was in the 1960s and 1970s that feminist theologies took shape as an academic discipline. It was inspired by liberation theologies and civil rights movements. An important voice of this period was Mary Daly. Her early work, *The Church and the Second Sex* (1968) unveiled the hegemonic patriarchal structure of the Catholic Church, refusing to or ignoring “the profound aspirations of half the human race to liberty and full personhood.” She challenges predominant male-centred image of God in her later work, *Beyond God the Father* (1973). Rosemary Radford Ruether, another significant feminist theologian, offered a reform-oriented approach. One of her proposals to evaluate Christian theology is in its ability to promote justice and the full humanity of women. Feminist biblical scholarship also saw its dawn during this period. Elisabeth Schüssler Fiorenza's scholarly work, *In Memory of Her* (1983), challenged androcentric interpretations of Scripture. She reconstructed early Christian history to recover women's leadership. Various Universities and seminaries played an important role in the development of feminist theology. The spread of

contextual theology led to the expansion of feminist theology beyond its early Western, predominantly white focus.

By the late twentieth century, feminist theology influenced by liberation theology began to emphasize the importance of culture, race, class, caste, and colonial history. Aruna Gnanadason is one of the few Indian feminist theologians who made a significant contribution in spreading feminist consciousness. She successfully linked feminist theology with the lived realities of women in postcolonial societies by challenging Western feminist assumptions and patriarchal structures within Indian Christianity. Likewise, Delores S. Williams in the development of womanist theology, wrote *Sisters in the Wilderness* (1993). She centres her theology on the experiences of Black women and challenges doctrines that portray suffering as redemptive. Everyday struggles of Latin women became a *locus of mujerista* theology. Ada María Isasi-Díaz played a key role in advocating Latina feminist theology, particularly in *En la Lucha* (1993). Asian feminist theology was further shaped by thinkers such as Chung Hyun Kyung, Kwok Pui-lan, Evangeline Anderson-Rajkumar, Shalini Mulakal, and many others, who integrate Christian feminist theology(s) with Asian religious traditions and postcolonial critique. Feminist theologians recognized that gender oppression is woven together with race, class, caste, sexuality, colonialism, and economic inequality. While global expansion enriches feminist theology, it continues to struggle concerning authority, method, and the goals of theological reconstruction.

2. CORE PRINCIPLES, METHODS, AND CRITIQUES

At its core, feminist theologies are a critical response to hegemonic patriarchy. Patriarchy is understood not merely as the rule of a patriarch, but as a system that operates in religious language, leadership structure, decision-making, moral teaching, and symbolic systems to construct and sustain the superiority of one gender, male. For example,

masculine God-language, referring exclusively to God as Father, Lord, or King; the strict male-dominated leadership hierarchy of the Catholic Church are seen as reinforcing male dominance by presenting it as divinely sanctioned. A universal defining feature of feminist theology is its use of women's experiences as a theological source. Alongside Scripture and tradition, women's lived realities shaped by family life, work, violence, sexuality, and exclusion are valid grounds for theological reflection. Thus, feminist theologies represent a radical departure from classical theology, which often gives importance to abstract doctrine over embodied life. The full participation of women in religious leadership, teaching, and ritual life has been a major point of advocacy of feminist theologians. This conviction is rooted in the women's experience that her female body is no barrier to its sacramentality and capacity to reveal Christ while the Church hierarchy resisting to acknowledge it.

Methodologically, feminist theology is interdisciplinary. It employs a hermeneutics of suspicion to question texts and traditions shaped by male dominance. The historical-critical analytical tool has helped to recover women's roles in early religious communities. Many feminist theologians are committed to constructive feminist theology to develop new symbols and interpretations, and narrative approaches that value storytelling and communal memory as theological data.

Critics, however, identify significant weaknesses. In its early Western form, feminist theology often relied on presumed uniform women's experience, which did not exist. Even though later feminist theologies addressed race, class, caste, and colonialism, reliance on experience as an authoritative source remains theoretically unstable. Another common criticism is its selective engagement with Scripture. Feminist theologies have been accused of conveniently accepting biblical texts that support gender equality as

authoritative while treating texts that appear patriarchal as products of historical and cultural context. Thus, it is unclear whether its conclusions arise from Scripture itself or from prior ideological commitments. Although feminist theologies have deeply influenced academic circles and church bodies have engaged feminist ideas in theory, its influence in concrete institutional change is limited. Finally, contemporary debates over gender and sexuality, including LGBTQIA+, makes its path more challenging.

CONCLUSION

Feminist theologies are not a single principle but a diverse and evolving project, constantly refining and redefining itself while challenging hegemonic structures. One of its important achievements is that it has initiated the conversation of how deeply power shapes religious belief and practices. Will feminist theology remain largely a critical academic endeavour or mature into a constructive theology capable of reshaping power structures, is an open question. What is certain is that its challenge to inherited religious authority has permanently altered the theological landscape. Issues of gender, power, inclusion, and context must now be taken seriously, even by theologians who are critical of feminist theologies.

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